

Metaphor in the academic mentoring of international undergraduate students: The Erasmus experience

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Metaphor use in university contexts has received some attention by the literature (e.g., Steen et al., 2010; Herrmann, 2011; Berber Sardinha, 2015; Littlemore *et al.*, 2011), which has mostly focussed on the language produced by academics. However, more dialogic forms of academic communications, where students are afforded opportunities for feedback on and discussion of opaque language use, are usually missing in the analyses of applied metaphor researchers. In order to partially redress this imbalance in research into metaphor in academic discourse, this article looks at lecturers' use of metaphor in one such dialogic type of communication –academic mentoring –and how international students respond to these language uses. I examine the frequency and functions of metaphor in 27 video-recorded conversations between Spanish Erasmus students and their lecturers at five different European universities. My findings reveal that lecturers use metaphor frequently in this context too, but that it does not appear to pose obvious problems for interaction, although misalignments between speakers can be observed.

Introduction

Detailed linguistic descriptions have allowed us to better understand the complex set of grammatical and lexical choices made by the participants involved in academic communication. The existing linguistic research, using perspectives ranging from genre (e.g., Swales, 1990) to register analysis (e.g., Biber, 2006), has greatly contributed to unfolding the complexities and variations of the language used in academia. Even the less visible and more dialogic genres of academic communication, such as seminars, tutorials or office hour consultations, have recently received a growing amount of research attention (e.g., Chiang, 2011; Farr, 2003; Limberg, 2010; Skyrme, 2010; Waring, 2002; Young, 2013).

These linguistic studies do not typically include metaphor in their analyses, a task mainly undertaken by what Deignan, Littlemore and Semino (2013) call the linguistic or discursive strand of metaphor research. For these researchers, the role metaphor plays in academic discourse deserves some attention. Thus, Steen et al. (2010) and Herrmann (2013) have been able to show how, from the perspective of register, metaphor is particularly frequent in academic prose, ahead of conversation, fiction and news. It seems that the particularly abstract nature of the language used in academic settings provides a context for metaphor to thrive. Other researchers, for their part, have focussed on more specific academic communicative events, in which metaphor has also been shown to play a role. To give but a few examples, metaphors have been demonstrated to make significant contributions to the rhetorical construction of academic genres as different as architectural reviews (Caballero, 2003, 2006), business research articles (Skorczynska and Deignan, 2006), economics textbooks (author, 2010) or lectures (Corts, 2006, Corts and Pollio, 1999, Low, Littlemore, and Koster, 2008, Beger, 2019). It seems obvious that any serious account of academic discourse cannot leave out this figure of speech.

However, the literature on metaphor, unlike general linguistic accounts, has not yet developed an interest in the more dialogic forms of communication that occur in universities: there exist very few studies on the use of metaphor in face-to-face academic interaction. The ones that exist (e.g., MacArthur, Krennmayr & Littlemore, 2015) focus on the analysis of specific aspects (i.e. SEEING metaphors) and have not undertaken a particularly needed general overview of the use metaphor in these academic events. Therefore, there seems to be a need to incorporate an in-depth exploration of those academic genres with a greater conversational component if we want to have a complete picture of the ways metaphor works in the academia.

The present article aims to contribute to our knowledge of the presence and roles of metaphor in academic conversation, by describing metaphor use in the academic mentoring of 27 Spanish Erasmus students at five different universities in Europe. To achieve this aim, the article will be organised as follows. First, it will provide a brief background of the literature on metaphor in academic contexts, with particular attention to existing studies on metaphor density and on academic genres that are closer to office hour consultations. Then, the Method section will describe the corpus used, i.e., the European Corpus of Academic Talk (EuroCoAT), together with the metaphor identification procedure and the different statistical analyses and tools used in our investigation. The Results and Discussion section will report on the quantitative and qualitative analysis of the data, describing the density and types of metaphors used in these conversations, before examining the major functions of metaphors in these mentoring sessions and how these manifested themselves at different points in the conversations. Finally, some general conclusions from the study will be derived.

Background

Metaphor frequency in discourse

We owe to Lakoff and Johnson (1980), in particular, and to Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) metaphor scholars, in general, the now widely accepted recognition that metaphor is ubiquitous and found in all types of texts. Later research, and more particularly the more linguistic strand of metaphor research, has modulated this general statement. Thus, metaphor researchers from the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam Metaphor Corpus (VUAMC) (see Steen et al., 2010) have found that, far from being favoured by writers of literary texts, metaphor is also frequently found in other types of text. Literary texts do have a relatively high metaphor density –11.9% according to Dorst (2011)– but

other registers like the news (Krennmayr, 2011) or academic prose (Herrmann, 2013) surpass this level, with 16.4% and 18.5% respectively. By contrast, a register like conversation clearly features on the low side of the spectrum with a density of 7.7% (see Kaal, 2012).

A good explanation of these results is provided by attending to some of the functional features of the specific register. This is what Berber Sardinha (2015) does with the help of Biber's multidimensional analysis. In a corpus tagged for metaphor alongside additional linguistic mark-up, the co-occurring features resulting from a statistical factor analysis are shown to be related to specific contexts or situations, used as proxies for the functional explanation behind those linguistic features. Thus, Berber Sardinha is able to establish that a high metaphor density is connected with texts with a higher informational value, rich on explicit reference and a non-narrative dimension. These particular factors would be at the heart of the high density of academic texts.

However, generalizations about metaphor density, which use a register perspective and work with averages, should also take into account that metaphors are not evenly distributed in texts. There may be stretches of text with very little use of metaphor while other portions may be filled with the so-called bursts or clusters (cf. Cameron and Stelma, 2004). These local eruptions of density are not random. They usually appear in particular textual contexts and are related to particular discursive functions of that specific text, although certain similarities have been established. Metaphor bursts have been shown to be used with 'edge effects' (Littlemore and Low, 2006) to mark the beginning, to set the agenda of a lesson (cf. Cameron, 2003), or to summarize the main points of a business text (Koller, 2003).

In the specific type of discourse analyzed in this article, i.e., oral language, metaphor bursts have been associated with yet another function of metaphor, that of

alignment. As Cameron (2003) explains, participants in a conversation can repeat or extend conventional metaphors as a way of demonstrating mutual understanding or diminishing the stress of a learning situation. Metaphor alignment would thus be the other side of the coin of alterity, a Bakhtinian concept that Cameron also uses to describe not only the gap between learner and expert, but also between the participants involved in another oral genre she has explored in depth, i.e., reconciliation talk (cf. Cameron, 2007).

Metaphor in education

Variations in metaphor density may also be connected to specific contexts of use. For example, language use in school settings generally displays significant uses of metaphor (Cameron, 2003). Metaphor fulfils important ideational (*the atmosphere is the blanket of gases*), interpersonal (*give yourself a little time*) and textual (*we'll come back in a moment to it*) functions in communication between teachers and learners. More generally, we find extensive use of metaphor when experts communicate complex concepts to non-experts (Nash, 1990; Cameron & Low, 2004). In these situations, it is natural to find the presence of 'tuning devices' (Cameron & Deignan, 2003), which are linguistic signals that a metaphor is being used (e.g., 'kind of' or 'sort of'), as they guide the non-expert in the interpretation of the metaphorical expressions.

In tertiary education the situation is not very different to that of school settings. Lecturers use metaphor to organize their discourse, frame problems, change topic, or for evaluative purposes (Corts & Pollio, 1999; Low et al., 2008). Furthermore, complex metaphor systems underlie entire disciplinary areas and belief systems. Examples of extensive uses of metaphor include: Container metaphors -e.g., *spill-over effects*- in economics (author, 2010; Boers, 1999), disease metaphors -e.g., *immunization against racism*- in politics (Mio, 1996), biology metaphors -e.g., *a growing market*- in business

(Morgan, 1996; Arleo, 2000), music metaphors -e.g., *building structures follow a rhythm*- in architecture (Caballero, 2003, 2006) or conduit metaphors -e.g., *convey a certain meaning*- in linguistics (Aitchison, 2003; Reddy, 1979). Thus, part of the process of disciplinary enculturation of the student of different subject areas involves becoming familiar with and understanding the metaphor systems or models that constitute particular theories or frame the problems that disciplines seek to explore and resolve (cf. Beger, 2011b).

Metaphor in university contexts can cause significant comprehension problems for international students, which may contribute to underachievement in their academic work. For example, in her study of the types of language problems encountered by Bangladeshi students studying at a British university, Littlemore (2001) found that metaphor and metonymy accounted for the majority of the items the students misunderstood. Furthermore, they were largely unaware of their misunderstandings, which affected their interpretation of the evaluative content of the lectures. In a follow-up study, Littlemore et al. (2011) observed that the use of metaphor and metonymy in academic lectures presented problems of interpretation and understanding to students whose first language was not English. The authors concluded that their findings were a cause for concern, because “ordinarily, the use of metaphor is a valuable teaching tool. Lecturers use it to explain, clarify, summarize, evaluate; to remind or challenge; and above all to make their lectures easier to understand” (Littlemore et al., 2011, p. 427).

Office hours

Lectures are not the only means by which academic content is communicated or shared. There are other more interactive teaching/learning activities in which students may engage in dialogue with their lecturers/tutors. Seminars, tutorials or office hour consultations provide opportunities for the kind of face-to-face interaction that might

allow lecturers to notice metaphor-related misunderstandings and to clear them up, or for students themselves to ask questions about problems related to metaphor. Indeed, these interactions between L2 students and staff are likely to be particularly valuable, because these students often join an academic programme that is already under way at the host university (in the second or third year of an undergraduate degree, for example, in the case of Erasmus students) and their previous experience of academic work may differ in important ways from the norms and expectations of the host institution or department.

To date very few studies (e.g. Littlemore et al., 2012; Littlemore et al., 2013; MacArthur, 2011a) have looked at metaphor in these more dialogic kinds of academic events, and, none, to the best of my knowledge, have attempted to offer a broad characterization, both quantitative and qualitative, of metaphor use in office hour consultations. This is in sharp contrast with the attention they have received from a more general discursive perspective, where we can find studies dealing with office hours from a Conversational Analysis (CA) framework (cf. Limberg, 2010) or undertaking their analysis using a corpus analysis (Biber, 2006; Biber and Conrad, 2009).

Biber and Conrad (2009) state that, even though they clearly fall under the category of academic interactions, office hours “employ most of the core linguistic features of conversation” (p.96). These features include adjacency pairs, repetitions, contractions, semi-modal and modal verbs, first and second person pronouns, frequent verbs and questions (cf. Biber & Conrad, 2009). However, other features distinguish them from conversation. The presence of discourse markers (*ok, well, all right, so*) is explained by the need to mark the change of topic, given they normally deal with more than one issue in a short time (subject-specific matters, assessment criteria, course

management, etc.). The importance of deictics (*this, here, etc.*) is warranted by the need to refer to written documents (e.g. assignments) and the high frequency of adverbial clauses, especially conditionals, is related to the “problem solving nature” of office hours, in which lecturers try to give an answer to the problems presented by the students (Biber & Conrad, 2009, p. 99). We do not know, however, whether metaphor is a feature shared by conversation and office-hour interactions, or one that distinguishes them. Depending on how often and in what ways it is used, metaphor can serve to reinforce the conversational or the more academic linguistic features of mentoring sessions.

The present article examines the use of metaphor in the academic mentoring of international students at five different universities in Europe, where Spanish undergraduate students were undertaking a period of study within the Erasmus programme. The focus is on the type of communication which takes place outside classrooms or lecture halls, most normally in a lecturer’s office, where a student may speak to a course tutor about anything s/he deems appropriate. In short, the main aim is to provide a quantitative and qualitative description of the importance of metaphors in mentoring sessions, an objective that will be developed by the following research questions:

RQ1: To what extent is metaphor involved in the kind of interaction that takes place in academic mentoring sessions? Are there any particular factors influencing the frequency with which metaphor is used in these academic events?

RQ2: How is metaphor used in academic mentoring sessions? What functions does it fulfil?

Methodology

Data and procedure

The data analysed here come from EuroCoAT (European Corpus of Academic Talk), a corpus of 27 video-recorded conversations between lecturers and Spanish undergraduate students at five different European universities between April and November 2012. This yielded a total of 5 hours, 47 minutes and 33 seconds of conversational data recorded (consisting of conversations lasting between 6 minutes 32 seconds and 22 minutes 22 seconds). The completed corpus comprised 57,270 words¹, of which 39,938 were uttered by the lecturers and 17,275 by the students.

The data being sought were to resemble, as far as possible, the kinds of interactions that take place in office hour consultations, when lecturers are available for individual consultations with students. To this end, the research team sought volunteers among Erasmus students at the five different universities involved, asking those willing to participate in the study to suggest the name of a lecturer they were currently being taught by in order to engage in a guided academic consultation with him/her that would be video-recorded, transcribed and later analysed. Once agreement had been reached with the lecturer, timetables for the recordings were set up.

All participants in this research (students and lecturers) were fully informed of the purpose of this research and their role in it, and signed a form declaring that they fully understood the nature of their participation and their right to request that the recording equipment be turned off if they felt uncomfortable being recorded. They likewise gave their consent to the data gathered being used for research purposes.

In order to ensure that the conversations would deal with academic topics (rather than others that might arise, such as personal problems the students were experiencing), students were asked prepare two or three questions for their lecturers on one of three

topics: written or other assignments that they had completed or were in the process of completing; the systems of assessment used at the host university for that particular subject; and/or difficulties being experienced in understanding the course contents. The lecturers were not informed in advance of the content of the questions, although they were made aware of the general areas that the students would wish to discuss.

Participants

The 27 student participants (11 male and 16 female) were all Spanish undergraduates spending between 5 and 9 months at universities in Ireland, England, the Netherlands and Sweden within the Erasmus programme, which makes it possible for students from participating universities to complete part of their degree at another university in Europe. All the undergraduate degree courses that these students were enrolled in were taught in English, an increasingly common phenomenon in higher education institutions across Europe (Coleman, 2006).

27 lecturers were involved in these conversations (5 participated in more than one session recorded). 14 of the lecturers were native (L1) speakers of English; the remaining 7 had different L1s: Greek (1), Spanish (1), Dutch (2), Chinese (1), Swedish (1) and German (1). In only one of these conversations, where Spanish was the first language of both participants, did there exist a shared language background. In all cases, the conversations were in English.

Transcription process

The video-recorded conversations were transcribed, using a slightly modified version of the conventions used for the Vienna-Oxford International Corpus of English (VOICE). For full details of the spelling and mark-up systems used, readers are referred to the research project website: http://www.eurocoat.es/web_sections_1/the_corpus_12 . To

ensure, as far as possible, the homogeneity of the 27 transcripts, each conversation underwent four stages: the first version of the transcript was the result of the work of a research assistant; this was then checked for accuracy by two other researchers independently. Any disagreements about the way elements of the conversation had been transcribed were discussed and resolved by the three researchers involved. Finally, all transcripts were proof-read and corrected by one person to ensure that the spelling and mark-up conventions had been consistently applied across the corpus. Each transcript was assigned a place identification (UE, UI, UNL and US, referring to a recording made in England, Ireland, the Netherlands and Sweden, respectively) followed by a number, referring to the order in which the recordings were made. Hence, UNL2 is the transcript of the second recording made at a university in The Netherlands. The transcripts were time-stamped at 30-second intervals.

Unlike other transcription methods, the approach taken here was neutral as to the status of speaker utterances as backchannels or full turns, although all overlaps were recorded. As has been noted (Tottie, 1991), it is often very difficult to establish the boundaries of backchannels, because what to the analyst might look like a backchannel may in fact be responded to by an interlocutor, lending it the status of a turn in the context of the interaction in which it was uttered. The time stamps and the numbering of the speaker utterances made it possible to chart the flow of metaphoric activity automatically in relation to each speaker in each conversation.

Identification of uses of metaphor in the corpus

In general terms, the procedure followed to identify potentially metaphorical uses of words is the one described by the Pragglejaz Group (2007). It is important to note at the outset that a limitation of this identification procedure (MIP) is that it adopts a solely linguistic –indeed *lexical*- approach to discourse– and does not take into account any

possible paralinguistic features of communication or non-verbal manifestations of metaphor (e.g. gestures) that may occur during a discourse event.

In the present study, the lexical unit was usually taken to be a word, i.e. a string of orthographic characters with a white space on either side. However, in line with Nacey (2013), certain multi-word units were treated as single lexical units. These were 1) compounds which, in the transcript, were written as separate words, as sanctioned by the *Oxford English Dictionary* (used as the basic reference for spelling throughout the transcripts). For example, ‘web site’ was treated as one lexical unit; 2) polywords or phrases with specific grammatical functions. For example, subordinating conjunctions like *as long as*, quantifiers like *a lot of* or *a bit of*, wh-question polywords like *how long...?* or disjuncts and conjuncts like *of course* or *by the way*, all of which contain a word that is potentially metaphorical. If such strings can undergo internal modification (for example, ‘a bit of X’ versus ‘a little/blind bit of X’) they were treated as decomposable into their component words. If they could not (e.g. *by the way* or *how long...?*), they were treated as polywords.

The identification of the potentially metaphorical use of the lexical units in each transcript was carried out in the first instance by one member of the research team and then checked by two others. In cases of disagreement over the identification of a metaphorically used word, these were discussed and resolved by the three researchers involved (cf. the same approach used by Littlemore et al., 2014).

All the metaphors found in the corpus were tagged to identify, in each case, the speaker (lecturer/student) or part of speech. They were also tagged, following Steen et al. (2010), for type of metaphor, to differentiate between direct metaphors whose basic and contextual meanings are explicitly contrasted (e.g. “[classes look] like as if you were entering into a huge coliseum or something”) and indirect metaphors where the

contrast between the two meanings does not need to be explicitly expressed (e.g. “how you structure that material is an important part of the assessment”).

Analyses

Text

The automatic retrieval of all metaphors in the corpus was carried out using WordSmith Tools 5.0 to calculate the overall density of metaphor use and to classify each instance. I also used this corpus analytic tool to trace the metaphor activity in each transcript and to analyze the bursts of metaphorical activity produced by one participant alone or by the two speakers involved in the conversation. The methodology used in the identification of metaphor bursts is based on Littlemore et al. (2014, p. 123). Thus, the average density is calculated over a span of 20 words and assigned to the intermediate point (i.e., at the 10th word), a process which is sequentially carried out for all the successive 20-word stretches of the text, which receive their calculated averages accordingly.

The tokenization process and the identification of multiword units were carried out using Wmatrix and the *Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners*.

Quantitative

Word frequency was calculated to a per 10,000 rate, as this is the convention for small corpora like ours, and the Average Reduced Frequency (ARF), a measure that takes into account both frequency and dispersion (Brezina, 2018), was also computed to identify those metaphors which are common throughout the corpus, thus avoiding the prominence of the repeated use of a specific metaphor in a few sessions.

Statistical analyses were carried out with the help of SPSS (v. 22.0). Since the statistical test chosen for the study (the t-test) requires independent samples, the entire corpus could not be used for this purpose as some lecturers were involved in more than one conversation. Therefore, a subcorpus of 22 conversations excluding all but one of the

meetings in which the same lecturer participated was used to compare the metaphor production of lecturers and students, which meant leaving out the following conversations: UE06, UE08, UI03, UNL03 and US02.

Results and discussion

RQ1: To what extent is metaphor involved in the kind of interaction that takes place in an academic mentoring session? Are there any particular factors influencing the frequency with which metaphor is used in these academic events?

The answer to RQ1 can be addressed from different perspectives. In what follows, I will concentrate on four aspects (metaphor density, most frequent metaphoric lemmas, metaphor bursts and types of metaphors) as they all help to formulate a more accurate quantitative representation of the relevance of metaphor in mentoring sessions.

Lexical measures	total	Mean	Min.	Max.	Std. Dev.	conversations
Words (tokens)	57,270	2121.1	1127	4063	708.1	27
Different words (types)	3198	372.8	277	595	93.7	27
MRWs	6,837	253.26	120	648	105.953	27
Different MRWs (types)	754	92.07	51	192	29.24	27
Metaphor density %		11.9	8.2	15.9	2.05	27

Table 1: EuroCoAT descriptive statistics: Variation in metaphor use across the 27 conversations

Metaphor density

A summary of the incidence of metaphor use in the entire corpus can be seen in Table 1 and full results for the individual mentoring sessions can be found in Appendix 1. As can be seen, the average metaphor density (11.9%) may be considered high when compared to the 7.7% found in the conversational register by the VUAMC team (Kaal, 2012), although not as high as written academic prose (18.5%) –or even non-native academic essays (Nacey, 2013). An initial evaluation would indicate that metaphor would join the group of features (i.e., discourse markers, deictics and adverbial clauses),

which Biber and Conrad (2009) identified as specific of office hour interactions with respect to everyday conversation.

Most frequent metaphors

The list of the most frequent metaphorical lemmas used in the corpus can also shed some light on the usage of metaphor in these academic interactions. As can be seen in table 2, many of the most common metaphorically related words could be described as “semantically empty” (Deignan, 2005). This is the case for prepositions (*in*, *about*, *to*, *on*, *at*, *from*), light or delexicalised verbs (*have*, *get*, *make*, *give*, *take*, *put*), signalling nouns (*thing*, *way*, *question*) and discourse oral markers (*exactly*). In other words, the 25 most frequent metaphorical lemmas, which account for more than half of the total number of tokens (54.6%), are metaphors not readily identified as such (cf. Krennmayr, 2017 for an account of the problems in their identification) because they are conventional and because their literal meaning is much less frequent than the figurative sense. The high ARF values show that these lemmas are all widely distributed through the corpus, and that they make a clear contribution to the metaphorical fabric of mentoring sessions. Other terms such as layer, stakeholder, and architecture were also highly frequent, but as a result of their repetition in a single conversation, they have lower ARFs.

Lemma	PoS	Tokens	Norm (10K)	ARF	ARF rank
<i>in</i>	prep.	746	130.3	427.01	1
<i>have</i>	v.	376	65.7	216.33	2
<i>about</i>	prep.	362	63.2	193.95	3
<i>to</i>	prep.	232	40.5	134.17	4
<i>on</i>	prep.	231	40.3	116.13	5
<i>thing</i>	n.	154	26.9	85.27	6
<i>at</i>	prep.	138	24.1	84.36	7
<i>get</i>	v.	152	26.5	76.88	8
<i>go</i>	v.	113	19.7	62.47	9
<i>from</i>	prep.	123	21.5	62.18	10
<i>exactly</i>	adv.	124	21.7	50.94	11
<i>make</i>	v.	84	14.7	50.34	12

<i>see</i>	v.	96	16.8	49.62	13
<i>look</i>	v.	85	14.8	43.42	14
<i>give</i>	v.	83	14.5	38.72	15
<i>way</i>	n.	75	13.1	37.84	16
<i>use</i>	v.	91	15.9	35.71	17
<i>take</i>	v.	77	13.4	34.61	18
<i>find</i>	v.	63	11.0	29.62	19
<i>part</i>	n.	52	9.1	26.22	20
<i>up</i>	part.	49	8.6	26.06	21
<i>focus</i>	v.	55	9.6	25.21	22
<i>last</i>	adj.	56	9.8	25.03	23
<i>put</i>	v.	41	7.2	23.92	24
<i>question</i>	n.	78	13.6	23.21	25

Table 2: Most frequent metaphor lemmas used

The list of the 25 most frequent lemmas also offers us a glimpse of some of the most common uses of metaphor in our corpus. These generally coincide with those identified by Semino (2005) in the construction of speech activity in general English, i.e., the expression of goal achievement, the reference to concept and ideas, and the negotiation and transactions of interpersonal meanings, which are conventionally expressed through metaphors.

Besides, these frequently used verbs – *see*, *look* or *focus*– point to the presence of SIGHT metaphors (see MacArthur et al., 2015 for a full development of this type of metaphor in mentoring sessions), which mostly take the form of a basic metaphor (Grady, 1998), i.e., UNDERSTANDING IS SEEING. As an example, we can see the following exchange between a student (JR) and a lecturer (OL), where both make ample use of these metaphorical verbs:

(1) JR: the other day e em we have **seen** this **part** e:

OL: okay

JR: **about** the quality of profit

OL: yes

JR : ratio e now really i am not sure about em a good em about a e: em w- why is the: the: good e **question about** the: em the bad resolution **in** the ratio but em i have em em i have e i **looked** for this information

OL: mhm

JR : e:m because the operation the operating profits e **fell by** this per cent

OL: oh okay so this is a quite a **large** quite a **large** decrease because when you left

er the other day i was thinking about this and i i couldn't remember the figures you had but i had a quick **look** at the COMpany and i could see that this here is a LOSS from what i from what i remember in the accounts can you recall if it is an operating LOSS this

Two other source domains, MOTION and LOCATION/CONTAINMENT, are also frequent in the list as shown by the group of prepositions already mentioned (in, about, to, on, at, from), the particle (up), the verb go, the noun part, and the adjective last. They are typically used in conventionalised ways that are characteristic of general conversation (e.g., *in English/Spanish; at the end/start/the beginning*) or of written academic contexts (e.g., *in the exam/ essay/ article/ introduction*) (cf. Bowden, 1993). However, we sometimes find other uses of MOTION and LOCATION that are more specific to the context of mentoring sessions:

(2) JW: so erm yeah you will have a number of different types of compounds that you're going to **go through** you will give examples of each type ...

[...]

JW: erm i think y- yes it will be useful to to show that er to to give the to give the erm hh er th- t- t- to give the the the the non-transparent meaning erm er it depends what else you're going to do there whether you whether y- there's much of an issue **from** the literature or not erm

ES: well it's **going** s- too

JW: hm

ES: **deep**

JW: exactly exactly erm it sounds like you're probably going to **go** too **far into** it (US01)

As we can see from the example, the lecturer (JW) is using here a SOURCE-PATH-GOAL schema to describe the process of writing, which is particularly useful to discuss the way (i.e., topics and the structure) essays need to follow. The student seems to notice the metaphor, as demonstrated by the expressions 'it's **going** s-' and '**deep**', but fails to actually realize that it is an EGO moving metaphor. She fails to identify herself as the 'mover' (i.e. writer) in the way the lecturer does by using 'you' as the subject of the movement verbs.

Finally, the importance of TRANSFER metaphors is signalled by the frequency of the use of light verbs such as give, make, or have:

- (3) and they're not corrected they're not given advice and guidance (UE1)
- (4) and he just makes a brief description about the three (UNL1)

Comparing lecturers and students

The statistically significant results of the t-test performed (see Table 3) clearly show a higher metaphorical density in lecturers' production in comparison to that of students (13.3% vs 8.9%), as highlighted by the p value and the large effect size shown by Cohen's d. Lecturers, as members of research communities, are familiar with academic registers, which display a great deal of metaphor use (Herrmann, 2013; Low et al., 2008). Consequently, they are more likely to use more metaphorically dense language than students who are undergoing the process of disciplinary enculturation in their L2. Given the similarity to the metaphor densities of the lecturers analysed by Low *et al.* (2008: 435), which ranged from 10% to 13%, it may be possible to conjecture some sort of stability in the oral language used by lecturers in academic settings.

	# words	#MRWs	MRWs (%)	SD	p value	t score	Cohen's d
Students	13,809	1278	8.9%	2.3			
Lecturers	33,801	4559	13.3%	3.4	0.000	4.93	1.49

Table 3: Metaphor density: students vs. lecturers (subcorpus with non-repeated lecturers)

The difference in metaphor use by lecturers and students can also be studied by looking at the individual metaphors preferred by these two groups of speakers. Table 4 shows the absolute frequencies (Frq.) and the relative frequencies normalised to 10,000 words (RF) of the 25 most frequent words presented above. In addition, the log-likelihood results comparing the use of the individual metaphors are included to identify which ones were used differently, at a statistically significant level, by the groups. To

avoid the possibility of type-I error, a Bonferroni-adjusted significance level of 0.002 was required.

As can be seen from the table, there are 9 metaphor lemmas used more often by lecturers. These lemmas comprise three prepositions (to, at, from), two light verbs (get and give), two SIGHT metaphor verbs (see and look), a MOTION metaphor verb (go) and a discourse marker (exactly). This finding may be due to some sort of underuse by students, probably related to their own developing metaphorical competence. On the one hand, it may be due to L2 users' propensity to vocabulary simplification (cf. Mauranen, 2012), particularly in what concerns structural or closed-class items such as prepositions and light verbs (with the exception of 'have' for L1 Spanish speakers, cf. Neff and Bunce, 2010), which means they usually select an item in detriment of others, and, on the other, it may have to do with their lack of complete mastery of academic English phraseology (Simpson-Vlach and Ellis, 2010), where some of these lemmas ('so we|you can **see**', '(you) can **look** at', 'take a **look**', '**go back to**'), play a relevant role .

The overuse of about by students, established here in comparison to the baseline defined by lecturers, probably shows that this is the default preposition to introduce a 'landmark topic' in the English language and that they have not yet mastered other prepositions (e.g. on or around) with a more specific and nuanced meaning (cf. Lindstromberg, 1996, p. 141). This is the case of the following unconventional use by a student, who uses about to indicate general subject matter:

(5) e:hh actually i'm going to base my (.) essay more about the em (.) theory
(US2:243)

lemma	Frq. Lecturers	RF (10K) Lecturers	Frq. Students	RF (10K) Students	Log- likelihood	Sig.		
in	427	126.33	173	125.28	0.01	0.926		
about	183	54.14	136	98.49	26.76	0.000	***	-
have	209	61.83	95	68.80	0.73	0.392		
to	155	45.86	31	22.45	15.32	0.000	**	+
on	153	45.26	44	31.86	4.48	0.034		
thing	97	28.70	38	27.52	0.05	0.826		
at	108	31.95	10	7.24	30.26	0.000	***	+
from	92	27.22	16	11.59	12.03	0.001	*	+
get	98	28.99	14	10.14	17.40	0.000	***	+
go	91	26.92	9	6.52	24.12	0.000	***	+
make	56	16.57	17	12.31	1.21	0.271		
exactly	86	25.44	10	7.24	19.52	0.000	***	+
see	69	20.41	10	7.24	12.01	0.001	*	+
look	66	19.53	7	5.07	16.42	0.000	**	+
way	53	15.68	8	5.79	8.71	0.003		
use	68	20.12	16	11.59	4.39	0.036		
give	69	20.41	6	4.34	20.31	0.000	***	+
take	51	15.09	12	8.69	3.29	0.070		
find	40	11.83	9	6.52	2.95	0.086		
last	31	9.17	22	15.93	3.76	0.052		
put	18	5.33	20	14.48	9.27	0.002		
back	30	8.88	11	7.97	0.10	0.757		
point	29	8.58	9	6.52	0.54	0.461		
question	49	14.50	16	11.59	0.63	0.428		
focus	25	7.40	24	17.38	8.63	0.003		

Table 4: Metaphors produced by Lecturers and Students

+ statistically significant greater use by lecturers

- statistically significant greater use by students

Metaphor bursts

In order to investigate metaphor bursts in the data, graphical representations of the average metaphor density across the conversations were inspected (see Appendix 2). By identifying the peaks of metaphoric activity, I was able to focus on what is going on in the discourse at that particular moment. As has been observed (e.g., Cameron & Stelma, 2004; Koller, 2003), metaphors do not tend to be evenly distributed in discourse, but rather occur in bursts, in response to different factors. In the case of the EuroCoAT corpus, however, it is impossible to make any generalizations about

increased metaphor production at different points in these conversations because the twenty-seven different transcripts revealed very different patterns (see Appendix 2), in line with the heterogeneity of metaphor use generally across the 27 conversations. Some displayed a relatively even distribution of metaphor use in the conversation (for example, UE4 or UI6), while others showed a more uneven spread of metaphors by one or both speakers (for example, UE3 or UNL3). That is, tracing the metaphor activity in the transcripts of these conversations revealed no systematic patterns of metaphor activity, although it could be observed that the students' production of metaphors tended to cluster at the beginning of the conversation, when they explained the reason for consulting their teacher or posed their specific question.

We can observe that the relative density of metaphors – or peaks of metaphor activity – were peculiar to the interactions themselves and could not be related to individual speaker preferences or topics of conversation that required more or less metaphor use in their expression. However, bursts of metaphor activity could indicate great explanatory effort on the part of a speaker (usually the lecturer) when some mismatch was perceived between the way a certain topic was understood by the two interlocutors. For example, there was a particularly intense use of metaphor by a lecturer in North American Literature at one point in a conversation (UI10 222-245 or minutes 9.45 to 10.45), which was not accompanied by any production of metaphor by the student participant. The particular topic being dealt with in this part of the conversation was how “coherence” should be understood in relation to an essay topic that the lecturer advised the student to choose. The lecturer (DC) had asked the student what she understood by coherence, and the student's response showed that she appeared to be relating “coherence” to sentences and paragraphs (grammatical relations), rather than to narrative form. In his explanation of how coherence could be related to

narrative, the lecturer repeated similar metaphors (“comes to a nice ending”; “everything is kind of wrapped up or tied up”; “all the loose ends are tied up”) in his attempt to clarify the point.

Types of metaphors

The figures given in Appendix 1 and Tables 1 and 2 record instances of indirect metaphors only, that is, metaphors realized by verbs (e.g. “the marks aren’t carried forward”), nouns (“we can treat the topic from different perspectives”), adjectives (“it’s just not high quality academic material”), prepositions and particles (“advice and guidance in the second year”; “look up those words”) or adverbs (“we wouldn’t grade you as harshly”), in which there is no explicit signal of a metaphorical comparison being made. In the context in which they were used, these were rarely² flagged as metaphors with the use of tuning devices (Cameron & Deignan, 2003) such as “kind of”, “actually” or “imagine”, for example. This is somewhat surprising because in their analysis of the language of Primary School teachers, Cameron and Deignan (2003) found that words and phrases such as these were used to direct the listener’s attention to a particular interpretation, adjust the strength of the metaphor or even alert interlocutors to the unexpected, showing a “high degree of sensitivity to notions about the hearers’ developing linguistic knowledge” (2003, p.157). In the academic conversations recorded, no such sensitivity to the Spanish students’ developing knowledge of English can be found, and the lecturers appeared largely unaware of any difficulties that metaphorical language might pose to them.

Furthermore, direct metaphors (those realized as A is B metaphors, comparisons with ‘like’, ‘as’ or ‘as if/though’, or extended metaphors) were very infrequent, although it has been argued (Steen, 2008, 2011) that such marked uses of metaphors may play an important role in communication – and in academic communication in

particular (Beger, 2011a) – because they signal clearly that the interlocutor is being invited to consider something in terms of something else. Only three such instances used by lecturers in our data are found (analysed in more detail by MacArthur, 2015, 2016). For example, a lecturer (US5) trying to explain the concepts of “amplification attack and control” and “reflection” in Computer Security drew an analogy with cue sports:

(6) Like for example don't you play pool? Do you play billiard? So instead of going directly to the ball you would then go to a corner first and then it would reflect and so instead of going directly to the ball, you would then go to a corner first and then it would reflect and hit it at a different angle³ (US5:72-78)

This direct signalling of a figurative comparison was also mostly absent in the students' speech, being used by only one student when he described the lecture halls at his home university:

(7) It looks like as if you were entering into a huge coliseum or something (UI3:171).

In short, neither lecturers nor students showed any great awareness of any need to signal that their language use was intended to be understood as non-literal; rather, in the vast majority of cases, metaphors were used covertly by all participants in these mentoring sessions.

As an interim summary, before we deal with our next research question, the quantitative role of metaphor in office hour consultations can be described in the following way:

- a. The presence of metaphor in these oral academic events can be considered as high both in absolute terms and by comparison to other oral registers like conversation. This finding would confirm the analysis by Berber Sardinha (2015), for whom metaphor is one of the features contributing to the information packaging and explicit-elaborated reference as typical functional dimensions of academic discourse (Biber, 1988). However, the lower levels

of metaphor density with respect to written academic prose would indicate that mentoring sessions do not play out these dimensions to their full potential, which is consistent with Biber and Conrad's characterisation as a hybrid genre (Biber and Conrad, 2009).

- b. Conventionality is a typical feature of the metaphors found as is demonstrated by some of the most frequently used metaphoric lemmas (prepositions and light verbs) as well as by use of primary metaphors related to a group of restricted target domains (SIGHT, MOTION, LOCATION/CONTAINMENT).
- c. Experts, i.e., lecturers, are the participants mostly responsible for the use of metaphor, but they hardly use direct metaphors or take the trouble to flag them, which seems to indicate a certain lack of awareness of the problems their L2 novice interlocutors may experience in their understanding. By contrast, students use fewer metaphors and tend to overuse some of them at the detriment of others used by their lecturers.

Functions of metaphor in academic consultations:

RQ2: In what ways is metaphor involved in the kind of interaction that takes place in an academic mentoring session? What functions does it fulfil?

The different functions fulfilled by metaphor in these academic conversations sets them, once again, apart from other academic genres. For example, unsurprisingly, they are different from those previously identified in lectures (Low et al., 2008). Furthermore, although monologic academic discourse may display relatively frequent uses of metaphors in organising discourse, this was infrequent in these conversations. For example, movement metaphors were used by two lecturers to defer discussion of a topic to a later stage of the conversation:

(8) I can try to explain and then if we need it we can go back to it" (US5: 68)

(9) Okay I'll come to the exam in a second (UE7: 21).

Cameron's (2007) analysis of the use of metaphor drew attention to the work done by metaphor in bridging "alterity", allowing speakers to explain themselves and understand others (Cameron, 2007, p. 197). The relatively high frequency of metaphor use in these academic conversations may similarly be accounted for by the work being done (principally by the lecturers) in bridging knowledge gaps.

Advice giving

The most important function of metaphor was in directives (or giving advice), which is of course closely connected with the purpose and topics of these academic mentoring sessions. As has already been mentioned, sight metaphors (realized by the verbs *see*, *look*, or *focus* or nouns like *view* or *perspective*) were very frequently used by the lecturers when directing students to think about or pay attention to some aspect of their academic work:

(10) Then you need to come together and you look at their insights and you get you can understand more (UI5)

(11) But on the other hand you might look and see, well, actually, when I look at those topics a couple of them actually go together (UE2)

(12) It doesn't matter that how many roles you define, but it really matter that you think about the system from your own perspective (UNL4)

When giving feedback on written assignments and talking about issues of clarity of exposition and text organization, lecturers often expressed this metaphorically, as the following two extracts from the corpus show. In the first, the use of metaphorical words like connect, expand, work, focus, approach serve the lecturer to give advice on the topic of a written assignment done for a Political Science module:

(13) The two don't really connect so you could have either sort of expanded on this one and to say like this is why this institution doesn't work, you know, lack of compliance mechanisms, lack of support in some countries, sovereignty problems. Sort of making this more extensive and focusing on when the institution doesn't work. Or you could have, instead of focusing on the institutions, you could have expanded on this section, which is, you know, here are the ideas about sovereignty, about cultural relativism, which you didn't have here, or about, you know, you have the two approaches the Kantian approach and ... "(UE3:113-123)

Another example also shows how a lecturer employed an extended metaphor to point out weaknesses in an essay a student had written about Oscar Wilde. In this case, verbs like follow, pick, or lift are used to reify the ideas used by the student:

(14) I think - but you need to correct me now- because when I read your essay it was sort of a little difficult to follow your train of thought. But I think that what you want to do is to say that he contradicts himself. That is your main point so this - this one thing is something that you need to pick out from your essay, lift out and make clearer This is your main idea. You're not talking about Oscar Wilde or the article. You are talking about how he contradicts himself in the article. This is your point and you need to lift it out (US3: 21-27).

Likewise, when advising on how to go about preparing a written assignment, lecturers would explain the particular criteria used in assessment that the students did not appear to be familiar with, using metaphorical language to communicate this. For example, a Business Studies student explained that "there are big difference because in my university in Spain we don't have to write the bibliography and we don't put any reference in the essay" (UE4). The lecturer expressed surprise at this ("Oh? I didn't know"), because he had just described the importance of providing adequate bibliographical support in the following terms:

(15) So in the guidelines that I gave you on the essay, you know, I try to emphasize that. Then, of course, on content there are - there are simple things that I'm looking for and that's the number of references and also the kind, the quality of references so, as I emphasized, it's very important in essays like this, to- for them to be driven by the the academic literature and and also to move away from text-books so so that is an important part of the of the story (UE4:26-32)

Given the student's ignorance of this aspect of academic writing, it seems very unlikely that she would have understood what the lecturer meant by an essay being "driven by the academic literature". This explains why, at the end of this exchange, the lecturer,

who has now realised the problem, feels prompted to categorically conclude in a less metaphorical way: “can't (.) you you can't submit (.) erm (.) essays certainly not for me without bibliography” (UE4:70).

As already mentioned, the students employed metaphors to ask questions or request advice about a problem they were experiencing:

(16) I know that I want to write about this but I don't know how to approach it
(UI2: 20)

Interestingly, one student's (DE) questions had to do with understanding the metaphors used to describe certain concepts in a course on Computer Security (“hijacking”, “reflection” and “amplification”). For example:

(17) DE: I was reading a (.) the (.) lecture notes em I know in this site
SB: mhm
DE: What er what does it sa- <reading aloud> work station hihacking </reading aloud> it's (.) I don't know
SB: er work station hijacking?
DE: mhm
SB: erm means that er if you're working on a work station and then you go away
(US5:3-10)

Thus, although in a lecture, the student would most probably be unable to ask about metaphors associated with the contents of a module, the mentoring session did provide the opportunity for the meaning of these terms to be cleared up.

A problem sometimes discussed concerned the differences between the knowledge acquired at the home university and that needed at the host institution, which one student expressed thus:

(18) The first I want to ask you is about if you can rec- recommend me a book 'cause in Spain I'm studying Biotechnology so I'm more focused on bionomic (unclear) field and I think I have some gaps in neuroanatomy and the brain
(UNL2: 03-05)

Metaphor was therefore not only necessary when students expressed the problems being experienced but could also comprise the focus of the problem to be discussed, as in computer security terminology.

Alignment

A final function identified in the sessions has to do with the systematic development of metaphors by the different interlocutors engaged in a conversation (Cameron et al., 2010). This systematic use of the same or similar metaphor vehicles can be argued to reveal a close coordination of meanings and understandings, a conversational move that Niederhoffer and Pennerbaker (2002) have termed *linguistic style matching*. Repetition and elaboration of another's words – metaphorical or not – have been shown to be important in spoken dialogic discourse as this helps build rapport and provides close connections, as well as contributing to topic development across turns (MacArthur & Littlemore, 2011; Tannen, 2007). The uptake of a metaphor – that is, its repetition or development – across turns is only one indication that the interlocutors have understood (at some level) the metaphorical frame being offered by replicating and collaborating in its use in the discourse.

An example of this particular use of metaphor by a student can be found in line 28 in transcript US3 and line 124 in UE3. There two different students picked up on a word used metaphorically by the lecturer (clearer→clear; approaches→approach) in their own following turns at talk. The best example, however, comes from a conversation that turned on exam preparation, in which a Business Studies student (DS) completed an analogy used by the lecturer (MO) when talking about the different types of readings a student should undertake in preparation for an exam. This other-completion revealed how closely the student was following the lecturer's explanation:

(19)MO: And look at it **as a pyramid**

DS: mhm

MO: and what you need to do is you you need to be exTREMElY familiar with the top s- the stuff at the TOP (.) you <53> have to know that </53>

DS: <53> but have the base </53>

MO: yeah exactly

(UI5: 283–289)

However, this kind of verbal behaviour was rare among the students, who showed a

preference for minimal responses to the lecturer's metaphoric formulations. For example, the cue games analogy used by the lecturer teaching a course on Computer Security, cited in (1), was met by uhu and mhm by the student, as was the lecturer's remarks on essay writing ("it's very important ... for them to be driven by the the academic literature and ... to move away from text-books") cited in (14). In these cases, the students did not give any clear verbal indication that they had understood what the lecturer was getting at or if the explanation was helpful.

If the students themselves showed little evidence of having picked up on their lecturers' metaphors, the same can be said for all except one of the lecturers. Although the students might have used metaphors in framing their problems or asking for advice, their interlocutors rarely repeated or elaborated on these formulations in their own answers, although on one occasion the more powerful conversational partners did challenge a student's metaphor. A lecturer (NT) teaching Academic Writing overtly corrected a student's metaphoric production, although this seems to have gone unheard by the student (MM).

(20) MM: So I have to figure out how to:
NT: how they are <53> connected</53>
MM: <53> mix </53> e:
NT: hm how they are <54> connected </54>
MM: <54> more things </54>
(UE2:148–152)

In contrast, a lecturer in North American Literature seemed to be paying close attention to a student's formulation of her problems in preparing a written assignment ("I don't know how to approach it" [UI2:20] and "I don't see how to do it" [UI2:42]) when he recycled and elaborated on her metaphors, using semantically related lexis (approach/pursue; look at/focus on) when offering advice on how to go about this particular assignment (MacArthur, 2016a deals EuroCoAT examples in more detail).

Repeating or elaborating on another's metaphors is not, of course, the only way that a student or lecturer can display comprehension of another's words. For example, part of the conversation between a lecturer in Biomedical Sciences and an undergraduate doing a degree in Biotechnology illustrates how different factors may combine to elucidate a metaphorical use of language, and how the student displayed his understanding of it. At this point in the conversation, the student (IS) was talking about an upcoming exam, remarking that "some lecturers are focusing on a particular field of research" and wondering whether the lecturer (HV) would be "asking in the exam about those particular things or ...more about general peculiarities":

(21) HV BOTH so er every lecture will be part of the exam and out of every lecture there will come (.) three to four multiple-choice questions (.) er I ask the lecturers to point the most important points of the er lecture er er to to tell them at the end of the lecture so these are the learning outcomes or take-home messages so I HOPE er: and the lecturers will tell you THESE
IS yeah
HV and then they will base their questions on the learning outcomes
IS ah
HV so I've k- I've instructed them not to focus on details (.) but on the the **red line** of their lecture
IS yeah to take home
(UNL2: 34-43)

As can be seen, IS signals that he has understood the gist of what the lecturer has said ("yeah to take home"), although "red line", with the meaning of "main point" or "thread (of an argument)", would almost certainly have been unfamiliar to him. This is not a conventional metaphor either in English or in Spanish, although it is in Dutch, the lecturer's L1. However, both the specific context in which it was used, as well as knowledge of Spanish, may well have aided comprehension. The lecturer had already referred to the "main points of the lecture" and "take-home messages", and said she instructed the other lecturers "not to focus on details", so understanding that the "red line of the lecture" means something similar to "the main points" is a reasonable

interpretation. On the other hand, the Spanish cognate for English “line” has a conventional metaphorical sense meaning “thread (of an argument)” (e.g. *su línea fue muy coherente* Lit ‘his line was very coherent’), which may have facilitated the student’s understanding of this calque from Dutch.

Conclusions

This article has offered a first look at the frequency, forms and functions of metaphor use in office hour conversations. The 27 mentoring sessions analysed indicate that metaphor is used no less frequently in academic dialogue than it is in academic monologue (Low et al., 2008) and indeed may be used more often by lecturers in conversation with individual students. This may be attributable to the different functions of metaphor in these two different contexts: in our data, metaphor was most frequently used to give students advice about their academic work, although this could be the result of the prompt they were given when collecting the corpus.

The Spanish undergraduates also employed metaphor in their talk, though less frequently than their interlocutors and for different purposes. However, we noted a great deal of variation in the use of metaphor among the undergraduate students.

Despite the variation in the density and functions of metaphor used by the different participants in these academic mentoring sessions, I found no clear cases of metaphor-inspired misunderstandings. Furthermore, the participants typically did not signal that their utterances were to be understood as metaphors, except in four cases (one student and three different lecturers) when an idea was expressed as a direct metaphor. The absence of overt attention to metaphor may indicate that the students were able to understand the advice and feedback they were being given, unlike the difficulties international students are reported to have with metaphor in lectures (Littlemore et al., 2011). On the other hand, previous research (e.g. Firth, 1996; House,

1999) has shown that L2 English interlocutors tend to avoid requesting clarification of another's utterances, even in the face of extraordinary or incomprehensible language uses, and it may be that the students were not in fact fully understanding the advice they were being given, as the lecturers suspected.

In this regard, the absence of much systematic development of metaphors across turns is perhaps a clearer indication of the lack of coordination of meanings and understandings between the dyads. In L1 conversational discourse, metaphors are developed and negotiated among participants in a conversation. In these conversations, the systematic use of metaphor was mostly a monologic achievement by the lecturers, and the students showed few signs of noticing this by echoing, developing or challenging the metaphors their interlocutor used. This may be a consequence of the roles adopted by the participants (mentors versus mentees) and the resulting asymmetry in the interactions a consequence of the differences in power between the two. On the other hand, given that the context of the interactions was adult education, one might expect – even hope for – more balanced interactions (as seen in UI3, for example) with the student interlocutors collaborating more actively in jointly constructing the learning that can take place in mentoring sessions such as these. It might therefore be necessary to train students in the specific interactional skills that would be needed in academic conversations with their lecturers, which would include the ability to repeat or elaborate on a lecturer's metaphorical production in order to show how or whether it has been understood. This would of course run in parallel with the need to make lecturers aware of the metaphors they use and the importance of using strategies to open them up for international students. In this respect, even though this would require further research, the elaboration of authentic materials derived from the corpus analysed here could provide successful examples of the use of metaphor in lecturer-students interactions,

which could be then expanded by providing practice in how a metaphorically dense turn by one speaker can be continued by his/her interlocutor by resorting to congruent metaphorical models. By contrast, examples in which students show little engagement in the conversation could also be used to practice alternative ways to develop the conversation by resorting to metaphorical alignment. Finally, a battery of exercises built around the systematic use of metaphor and including some of the most frequent metaphors used in oral academic language (e.g., UNDERSTANDING as SEEING or WRITING/READING as MOVEMENT) may also be a way of exploiting some the results of the present research.

¹ These were the tokens used for generating word lists, and did not include items not found in dictionaries, such as hesitation markers like *mhm* or the orthographic representation of speaker sounds, such as *haeh*. This figure also comprises the (few) words spoken by the researchers in three conversations to give an indication to the participants about the timing of the session. The tokenization process and the identification of multiword units were carried out using Wmatrix and the *Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners*

² The exception to this was the L1 Greek lecturer in UE3, who used “sort of” before words used metaphorically and non-metaphorically.

³ For reasons of readability, and to excerpts from the transcripts have been greatly simplified. Access to the full transcripts can be obtained at www.eurocoat.es

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ANNEX 1. Summary table of EuroCoAT corpus

File	MRWs Student	Tokens Student	Density Student	MRWs Lecturer	Tokens Lecturer	Density Lecturer	MRWs Resear-cher	Tokens Resear-cher	MRWs Session	Tokens Session	Density Session	Country	Subject Domain
UE01	38	561	.07	275	1740	.16	5	19.00	313	2325	13.46	ENGLAND	HUMANITIES
UE02	57	698	.08	194	1478	.13			251	2176	11.53	ENGLAND	HUMANITIES
UE03	115	971	.12	187	1515	.12			302	2486	12.15	ENGLAND	SOCIAL SC.
UE04	31	388	.08	108	1095	.10			139	1483	9.37	ENGLAND	SOCIAL SC.
UE05	67	766	.09	98	879	.11			165	1645	10.03	ENGLAND	HUMANITIES
UE06	42	393	.11	138	1209	.11			180	1602	11.24	ENGLAND	HUMANITIES
UE07	35	506	.07	220	1598	.14			255	2104	12.12	ENGLAND	HUMANITIES
UE08	44	481	.09	156	1256	.12			200	1737	11.51	ENGLAND	HUMANITIES
UI01	52	467	.11	135	1116	.12			187	1633	11.45	IRELAND	SOCIAL SC.
UI02	67	849	.08	215	1629	.13			282	2478	11.38	IRELAND	HUMANITIES
UI03	130	1387	.09	232	1844	.13			362	3231	11.20	IRELAND	HUMANITIES
UI04	75	876	.09	199	1718	.12			274	2594	10.56	IRELAND	SOCIAL SC.
UI05	159	1146	.14	489	2917	.17			648	4063	15.95	IRELAND	SOCIAL SC.
UI06	17	415	.04	280	3202	.09		24.00	297	3641	8.16	IRELAND	SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
UI07	47	623	.08	168	1280	.13		9.00	215	1912	11.24	IRELAND	SOCIAL SC.
UI08	37	432	.09	153	1324	.12			190	1756	10.82	IRELAND	SOCIAL SC.
UI09	48	806	.06	364	2216	.16			412	3022	13.63	IRELAND	SOCIAL SC.
UI10	67	862	.08	202	1579	.13			269	2441	11.02	IRELAND	HUMANITIES
UNL1	42	476	.09	156	1261	.12			198	1737	11.40	NETHERLANDS	HUMANITIES
UNL2	48	468	.10	76	858	.09			124	1326	9.35	NETHERLANDS	SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
UNL3	48	486	.10	72	641	.11			120	1127	10.65	NETHERLANDS	SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
UNL4	34	253	.13	219	1404	.16			253	1657	15.27	NETHERLANDS	SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
US01	75	679	.11	238	1341	.17			313	2020	15.50	SWEDEN	HUMANITIES
US02	75	719	.10	204	1187	.17			279	1906	14.64	SWEDEN	HUMANITIES
US03	24	264	.09	157	1289	.12			181	1553	11.65	SWEDEN	HUMANITIES
US04	76	897	.08	126	1270	.10			202	2167	9.32	SWEDEN	SOCIAL SC.
US05	40	406	.10	181	1042	.17			221	1448	15.26	SWEDEN	SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING

Annex 2. Representation of moving metaphor densities by individual mentoring sessions

The y axis represents metaphor density in %; the x axis represents the progression of the session marked by the word number.